

Asymmetric Reduction. Part III¹. Reduction of Aryl Alkyl Ketones with Chiral Alkoxyaluminodichlorides and Studies on the Nature of the Transition States

D. NASIPURI and P. R. MUKHERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur 721 302.

A series of phenyl alkyl ketones are reduced asymmetrically by (-)-isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride (I). The results are rationalised in terms of four competing transition states which contain a linear C...H...C bond, the groups on the carbons being staggered with the two opposite dipoles (C=O and AlCl₂) forming a loose complex. Their relative contribution is determined by the steric and electronic effects of the substituents. The model explains all available data and clarifies some long-standing anomalies in asymmetric hydride transfer reactions.

Acetophenones substituted differently at the para position undergo reduction with the reagent (I) with almost identical asymmetric induction showing that rate does not affect it significantly. Treatment of chloroalumino-complex of racemic isborneol and borneol (excess) with chiral ketones affords optically active camphor, the configuration of which correlates with that of the ketone thus providing an easy method for determination of the same for an unknown chiral ketone. The effect of the pendant gem-dimethyl group in borneol on the stereochemistry of reduction is discussed. Addition of Lewis acid like magnesium bromide to ketone before reduction increases the yield and stereoselectivity of the reaction with isborneol reagent, as predicted from the above model.

Recently, there has been an upsurge in research activity in the field of asymmetric synthesis among the world chemists. The reason is partly man's ambition to emulate nature in her hundred percent efficiency in stereoselectivity brought about by enzyme systems. In a few instances, he has almost succeeded in doing so². Besides, asymmetric synthesis helps to avoid the intricacies and tedium of optical resolution and gives a better understanding of the subtle roles played

by steric and electronic factors in the transition state of a reaction. One major type of asymmetric synthesis which has been widely investigated during the past years utilises chiral aluminium alkoxides³, Grignard reagents^{4,5}, alkoxy magnesium halides⁶, and metal hydrides complexed with chiral alcohols^{7,8}, which reduce ketonic and other electrophilic double bonds by asymmetric hydride transfer.⁹ To this growing list, we have recently added a new class of reagents, namely, dichloroaluminum derivative of chiral alcohols such as isborneol and borneol, which reduce cyclic¹⁰ and acyclic^{11,12} ketones with a high degree of stereoselectivity. The advantages of these two reagents are their commercial availability in optically pure form, high reducing power under mild conditions, and almost complete irreversibility in their reaction.¹⁰ The reagents could also be easily prepared in their α -deuterated forms and used for asymmetric deuterium-transfer reaction.¹ Moreover, some study has already been made about the transition state of the reaction¹³ which proceeds seemingly through Whitmore's cyclic mechanism¹⁴ analogous to that generally accepted for Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley reduction. Very high asymmetric induction has been obtained with these reagents specially in the reduction of phenyl alkyl ketones.¹¹ The purpose of this communication is to furnish the experimental details, to elaborate some of our earlier views^{15,16} rationalising the present and some earlier data on asymmetric reduction, and to provide experimental evidence in their support wherever possible.

A mixture of (—)-isborneol (90%) and (+)-borneol (10%) obtained from reduction of (+)-camphor with lithium aluminium hydride was used for the preparation of isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride, the reduction due to borneol being negligible in comparison and therefore ignored. Pure (—)-borneol

obtained by hydrolysis of (—)-bornyl acetate was used for the preparation of the corresponding borneol-complex. The reduction was carried out either by first preparing a 'mixed hydride' solution¹⁷ and adding to it an equimolecular amount of the chiral alcohol followed by the ketone (Method A), or by preparing a solution of lithium aluminium tetra-alkoxide from lithium aluminium hydride and the chiral alcohol, adding the ketone to it, and then introducing an ethereal solution of aluminium chloride dropwise (Method B¹⁸). It is difficult to know what is the exact nature of the reagents or whether they are the same in both the cases. However, the stereoselectivity of the reagents prepared by either method was the same in the present instances within experimental error.

They are conveniently formulated as alkoxyaluminium dichlorides in its monomeric form [as I from (—)-isoborneol]. The alcohols obtained after reduction were purified by taking advantage of their lower steam volatility compared to the camphoraceous impurities, and further by conversion into acid phthalates and regeneration. In a few cases, preparative g.l.c. was used. The final purity was checked by analytical g.l.c. The results of the asymmetric reduction of a number of phenyl alkyl ketones are given in Table 1 (entry 1) along with relevant data from earlier literature for comparison.

The data in Table 1 present one common feature: the absolute configuration of the preponderant

TABLE I—ASYMMETRIC REDUCTION OF RCOR¹ WITH DIFFERENT CHIRAL REAGENTS

Entry	Reagent	R	Percent Asymmetric Reduction (% e.e.) ^a with R ¹ equal to :										Confign.	Ref.
			D	Me	Et	n-Pr	i-Bu	i-Pr	C ₆ H ₁₁ ^b	t-Bu	Ph			
1	(—)-Isobornyloxyaluminium Dichloride (I)	Ph	10	25	38	44	66	84	40	35	—	R	1,15 ^e	
2	S-(+)-2-Methylbutylmagnesium Chloride	Ph	19	4	6	6	10	24	25	16	—	S	9(p.183)	
3	S-(+)-2-Phenylpropylmagnesium Chloride	Ph	—	38	38	—	—	59	—	(22) ^d	—	S	9(p.188)	
4	S-(+)-2-Phenylbutylmagnesium Chloride	Ph.	—	47	52	—	53	82	—	16	—	S	9(p.188)	
5	S-(+)-3-Methyl-2-phenylbutylmagnesium Chloride	Ph	—	66	—	—	—	80	—	91	—	S	9(p.188)	
6	Isobornylmagnesium Chloride ^e	Ph	—	36	19	46	—	55	—	72	—	R	4	
7	(—)-Isobornyloxyaluminium Dichloride(I)	Me	—	—	2.8	—	5	16	—	18 20 ^f	25	R	12	
8	S-(+)-2-Methylbutylmagnesium Chloride	t-Bu	12	13	11	11	6	0	2	—	16	S	9(p.183)	

^ae.e.=Enantiomeric excess. ^bC₆H₁₁ stands for cyclohexyl group. ^cSome of the data have been revised. ^dBracket indicates configuration opposite to that labelled for the series. ^eGrignard reagent from 'pinene hydrochloride' made from (+)- α -pinene. ^fRef. 18.

enantiomer in each case (with a lone exception shown in parenthesis) is predictable from the consideration of steric interactions in the two diastereoisomeric cyclic transition states, the one with the two larger groups of the carbinol and ketone oppositely placed being preferred (e.g., III from II). When the groups involved are purely aliphatic (Table 1, entries 7 and 8), the model satisfactorily predicts also the relative order of asymmetric induction: the greater the bulk difference of the groups, the higher the stereoselectivity. But when a phenyl group is introduced in the substrate or in the reagent, the expected order of asymmetric induction shows a trend in the reverse direction (Table 1, entries 1-6)—the bigger the alkyl group, the higher is the asymmetric induction, although phenyl still behaves as the bulkier group of the two! Apparently, the simple concept in which the differences in activation energies is based solely on steric ground is no longer tenable. Other factors such as electronic interaction (e.g., electrostatic repulsion between two phenyl rings when both the ketone and the reagent contain phenyl¹⁹), rate of the reaction (the slower the rate, the greater the stereoselectivity), restriction in rotational conformation of the phenyl as the alkyl group changes its size²⁰, and the shifting of the transition state along the reaction coordinate with change of reactants should also be taken into consideration.

The key interaction however seems to be that of the two groups on the ketone and Brewster²¹ suggested that the larger the "small" group, the more the "large" group must turn away from it and thus seems to an external agent even larger. But there appears to be an element of contradiction in the statement since the external agent, namely the two groups in the carbinol, will "see" both the alkyl and the phenyl group appearing simultaneously larger. Evidently, as pointed out by Mosher¹⁹ and also by Felkin²², the origin of this discrepancy lies in some subtle electronic effect of the phenyl ring.

In 1967, an attempt was made from our laboratory¹⁵ to explain the anomalous behaviour of phenyl alkyl ketones from a purely steric point of view based on an assumption, which seemed to have some experimental support at that time^{1,23}, that the slower the rate of reduction, the higher is the stereoselectivity. It was argued that the branching at the α -carbon in passing through Me, Et, n-Pr, i-Bu, and i-Pr groups should not increase the effective bulk of the alkyl as long as it contained one α -H, since according to a model proposed by Karabatsos²⁴, the reagent (H^-) would still approach from the side

of this hydrogen (smallest group). Since the other two α -substituents are too far away to have any appreciable interaction with the groups on the asymmetric carbon in such a model (for details, see ref. 15), the energy difference between pairs of transition states would remain reasonably constant throughout the series. However, the slower rate of reduction as one passes through methyl to isopropyl²⁵ (due mainly to electronic factor) would result in an increased stereoselectivity. Only with t-butyl ketone, the steric situation in the transition state would change appreciably with a consequent drop in asymmetric induction. However, as pointed out by Morrison and Mosher (Ref. 9, p. 189) and also supported by our own experiments (*vide infra*) as well as theirs (ref. 9, p. 202), the rate factor does not significantly affect the stereochemistry in these reactions. Besides, some of the results (Table 1, entries 5 and 6) showing highest asymmetric induction with phenyl t-butyl ketone would still remain unexplained.

Meanwhile, it has been suggested that in these reactions the most favoured hydrogen transfer is possibly linear²⁶, be it through a cyclic transition state (IV)²⁷, or an acyclic one (V)²⁸.

During the past few years, on several occasions²⁹, we have been suggesting a transition state (VII) applicable to (—)-isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride (as VI), to explain the observed facts. It is very similar to the one proposed by Mathieu²⁷ but differs from it in two important aspects: (i) the model has been twisted along C..H..C axis to relieve steric and torsional strain and (ii) the two oppositely developing dipoles, $O^{\delta-}$ and $XM^{\delta+}$ (M stands for halogenated Mg and Al, X for CH_2 or O) are loosely bound through space thus avoiding rigidity of the cyclic model (IV). The transition state is reactant-like and the steric interactions may be appraised from Newman type of formulae (VIII—IX), viewed along C..H..C axis, the relatively short C-H bond and almost radial distribution of the groups in the

chiral centres largely compensating for the H-atom sandwiched between them. The distance between the two carbons in model (VII) may be approximately calculated from the equation (1)^{26,30}:

$$r_1 + r_2 = 2 \times 1.08 - 0.6 \log x (1-x) \quad (1)$$

where x and $1-x$ are the bond order and 1.08 \AA is the C-H bond length.

This is borne out by the data of Table 1*. Now if R is gradually increased in bulk, a buttressing effect will operate in both the conformations: rotation to separate L and R in IXa will push Ph and L together whereas a similar rotation in VIIIa is quite easy. Conformation IXa is thus further destabilised and more of R-alcohol forms resulting in a higher asymmetric induction with increasing bulk of the alkyl group. Anomalous results in reduction of t-butyl

Of the six transition states that could be envisaged for the reduction of PhCOR , only four (VIIIa, VIIIb, IXa, and IXb) are of real significance because they have the opposite dipoles gauche to each other permitting them to form a loose bond. The transition state (V) proposed by Welvert on the basis that the two negative ends of the activated complex would preferably be anti necessitates the separation of a species, Mg^+Cl (slow step)³¹ and is probably applicable to the systems(V) only, where formation of a six membered metal chelate is unlikely.³² Between the two conformations, VIIIa and VIIIb leading to R-alcohol, VIIIa is favoured both sterically (L and Ph anti) and also electronically ($\text{XM}^{\delta+}$ placed between two negative dipoles). Similarly for the formation of S-alcohol, the transition state (IXa) is favoured electronically, assessment of steric interactions being uncertain in this case. The product ratio R/S will therefore be determined mainly by the free energy difference between VIIIa and IXa and will certainly be in favour of R (compare the interactions $\text{Ph} \leftrightarrow \text{S} + \text{LO} \leftrightarrow$ in VIIIa against $\text{Ph} \leftrightarrow \text{L} + \text{S} \leftrightarrow \text{O}$ in IXa).

phenyl ketone may be due to a combined effect of noncoplanarity and consequent change in steric and electronic interactions of phenyl group as suggested by Mosher. On the other hand, in the case of purely aliphatic ketones, the contributions of the other transition states, VIIIb and IXb could not be wholly ignored. Between these two, IXb is of lesser energy (compare $\text{L} \leftrightarrow \text{R} + \text{S} \leftrightarrow \text{O}$ in VIIIb against $\text{S} \leftrightarrow \text{R} + \text{L} \leftrightarrow \text{O}$ in IXb) and so will have an opposite effect on asymmetric induction, although there could still be an overall preference for R-alcohol. This may explain the rather curious observation that in spite of the comparable size of phenyl, t-butyl, and cyclohexyl, there is no parity in the percent asymmetric reduction of alkyl ketones bearing these groups. To cite an extreme case, phenyl, t-butyl, and cyclohexyl isopropyl ketones when reduced with the same reagent, S-(+)-2-methylbutylmagnesium chloride gave alcohols of optical purity of 24, 5, and 2% respectively³³. With

* Reagents in entries 1, 6, and 7 in Table 1 have absolute configuration as VI while the rest have opposite configuration.

cyclohexyl and t-butyl ketones, the participation of VIIIb and IXb evidently reduces the stereoselectivity to a considerable extent.

A very perplexing observation has been reported from Mosher's laboratory (ref. 9, p. 191) when phenyl trifluoromethyl ketone is reduced with S-(+)-2-methylbutylmagnesium chloride. The corresponding carbinol was obtained with a 22% excess of an enantiomer with configuration opposite to that predicted on steric ground. According to the present model, the two most contributing transition states will now be VIIIb and IXb ($R=CF_3$) instead of VIIIa and IXa, assuming that trifluoromethyl is more electronegative than phenyl and therefore be placed preferably gauche to $XM\delta^+$. The enantiomeric ratio will accordingly depend on the relative stability of VIIIb and IXb between which IXb has already been proved to be of lower energy on steric ground. Trifluoromethylphenylcarbinol of configuration corresponding to IXb ($R=CF_3$) will therefore predominate,

X

XI

XII

which according to Cahn-Ingold-Prelog convention is designated as R-alcohol (S in case of alkylphenylcarbinols). It might be pointed out that Mosher's reagent had S-configuration opposite to that of VI used in this discussion and his alcohol was consequently rich in S-enantiomer. The same argument goes for the results with other trifluoromethyl ketones reported by these authors. Very high asymmetric induction (47-74%) has been obtained in reduction of these ketones when the Grignard reagent also contains a phenyl group⁹. This is conceivably due to a reinforcement of the steric effect by an electronic interaction in favour of IXb, the two negative groups, CF_3 and Ph being gauche in VIIIb ($R=CF_3$, $L=Ph$) but anti in IXb. Thus the anomalous behaviour of CF_3 acting as though it is much larger than Ph contrary to all other evidences, is explained.

There are one or two further points in our own work, which need clarification. Benzaldehyde-l-d when reduced with bornyloxymagnesium bromide and

bornyloxyaluminium dichloride, both from (-)-borneol, afforded respectively R(-)- and S(+)-benzyl- α -d alcohol of high optical purity (65 and 33% respectively)¹. The preponderance of R-alcohol from the former reagent was expected from the preferred transition state (X) (cf. VIIIa), on the assumption that C_1 -Me side of camphor is more crowded than the C_3 -methylene. But the formation of S-alcohol from a reagent which differs only in the metallic part but otherwise identical requires explanation. We suggest that $ROAlCl_2$ being a stronger electrophilic species than $ROMgBr$, the bond between $O^{\delta-}$ and $-AlCl_2$ becomes more tight in the transition state (X) which consequently closes up to the cyclic model (XI). The overhanging C_9 -methyl in the camphor nucleus now introduces an additional steric interaction with Ph as shown (XI). This reverses the stability order, the transition state (XII) with the two large groups on the same side being now preferred and S-alcohol forms predominantly. This has indeed been found true in several other instances.²⁴

It leaves us to the general conclusion that while the magnesium derivatives of alcohols as also the Grignards react with ketones through the *staggered* transition states (VIII-IX), previously¹⁶ called "acyclic", the corresponding dichloroaluminoketones probably react through the more *eclipsed* transition states (as XI), previously¹⁶ called "cyclic". As a result of the eclipsing effect, one would expect higher asymmetric induction with the alkoxyaluminium dichlorides. On the contrary, all the available data show that alkoxyaluminium bromides are by far the more stereoselective (see Table 2).

In our opinion, in the "cyclic" transition state (XI and XII), there will be considerable deviation in the linearity of the C-H-C bond. The ring is not necessarily planar and may tend to assume a chair-like conformation in which the two larger groups, ordinarily on opposite sides, be better accommodated in cis configuration. As a result, the difference of energy in the "cyclic" transition states will be lower

TABLE 2—ASYMMETRIC REDUCTION WITH ALKOXYMAGNESIUM BROMIDE AND ALKOXYALUMINIUM DICHLORIDE^{1,6,34}

Entry	Reagent	Aldehyde	% e.e.	Confign.
1	(—)-Isobornyloxyaluminium Dichloride	PhCDO	10	R
2	(—)-Isobornyloxymagnesium Bromide	PhCDO	52	R
3	(—)- α -d-Isobornyloxyaluminium Dichloride	PhCHO	18	S
4	(—)- α -d-Isobornyloxymagnesium Bromide	PhCHO	64	S
5	(—)-Isobornyloxyaluminium Dichloride	PhCOCO ₂ H	8	S
6	(—)-Isobornyloxymagnesium Bromide	PhCOCO ₂ H	15	S

than in the "acyclic", with consequent drop in stereoselectivity. When both the carbinol and ketone bear heavy substituents, the "cyclic" model would be destabilised due to 1, 3-interaction and may open up to the "acyclic" one. This is probably the case with alkyl phenyl ketones so that the results of reduction with isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride follow the same pattern as the others in Table 1. This dual mechanism also explains the otherwise incomprehensible fact that in most cases, RCHO and RCDO are reduced with equal or even less stereoselectivity than RCOMe (ref. 9, p. 183). Evidently, the steric encumbrance or the lack of it would push the transition state towards one way or the other with concomitant change in asymmetric induction.

The model lacks the simplicity of Whitmore's cyclic mechanism but otherwise explains satisfactorily all the available data on asymmetric hydride transfer reactions using organometallics. While no direct evidence could be provided in its support, some relevant points apropos of our previous discussion are capable of experimental verification. They are discussed below.

Rate of reduction was previously considered to be a vital factor^{15,19} in determining the stereoselectivity of these reactions. To verify its validity, a series of p-substituted phenyl methyl ketones and two phenylglyoxylic esters were reduced under comparable conditions. The data are given in Table 3. In most cases, the reduction went quantitatively. The optical purity of the halogenated alcohols was determined by con-

verting them into phenylmethylcarbinol on catalytic reduction in presence of triethylamine. Possibility of partial racemisation of mandelic esters during hydrolysis was apprehended but found to be negligible by comparing the rotation of a hydrolysed mandelic ester with that of a glycol derived from it³⁶. The results (Table 3) clearly show that aryl ketones substituted differently at the para position and therefore of different reactivity underwent reduction with the same degree of asymmetric induction within experimental error. Rate therefore does not alter the stereoselectivity significantly. Meanwhile, same conclusion has been reached by other workers³⁷ using Grignard reagents. The formation of neopentyl-1-d alcohol with 12 and 36 per cent enantiomeric excess respectively by a hydride transfer and a deuterium transfer (a slower reaction) from 2-methylbutylmagnesium chloride²³ which constituted a strong case for the effect of rate has now been attributed by Morrison* and Mosher to a possible "tunnelling" effect of hydrogen³⁸. The purity of the alcohol has also been questioned.⁹

Bornyloxyaluminium dichloride is a particularly interesting reagent because in some cases^{1,34}, it yielded preponderance of an alcohol the configuration of which can only be reconciled by invoking the interaction of the pendant C₉-methyl in a "cyclic"

* In preliminary communication¹⁶, we inadvertently made a wrong interpretation of the term, "isotopic disparity" used by Dr. Morrison in his review²². The words in the parenthesis on page 1, line 16 in ref. 16 may be ignored.

TABLE 3—ASYMMETRIC REDUCTION OF SUBSTITUTED PHENYL KETONES

Entry	Ketones	Reagent ^a	Yield ^b (%)	% e.e.	Confign.
1	PhCOMe	(—)-IsoB	100	25-27	R
2	<i>p</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COMe	(—)-IsoB	100	25 ^c	R
3	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ COMe	(—)-IsoB	100	28	R
4	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ COMe	(—)-IsoB	100	25	R
5	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ COMe	(—)-IsoB	0 ^d	—	—
6	<i>o</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ COMe	(—)-IsoB	0 ^d	—	—
7	<i>m</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ COMe	(—)-IsoB	100	30	R
8	PhCOCO ₂ Et	(—)-IsoB	—	14 ^e	S
9	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ COCO ₂ Et	(—)-IsoB	—	17 ^{e,f}	S
10	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ COCO ₂ H	(—)-IsoB	0 ^g	—	—
11	PhCOCO ₂ Et	(—)-B	—	10	S
12	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ COCO ₂ Et	(—)-B	—	12	S

^aIsoB stands for isobornylaluminum dichloride and B for bornylaluminum dichloride. ^bBased on g.l.c. analysis. ^c*p*-Nitrophenylmethylcarbinol was resolved through the brucine salt of its acid phthalate and had $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{30}$ 73.6°. ^dCould not be reduced under any condition. ^eRotation was taken for mandelic acid. ^fMaximum rotation reported³⁵ $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{19}$ 146.14° (H₂O). The acid formed an insoluble complex with the reagent.

transition state (XI). On the other hand, this effect appears to be absent in the corresponding bromo-magnesium-complex. To investigate this phenomenon further, four chiral ketones, namely, (1R, 4S)-(—)-menthone (XIII), R-(+)-3-methylcyclohexanone (XIV), (1S, 4R)-(+)-fenchone (XV), and 3-cholestanone were treated with 2 moles of dichloroaluminum complex of (±)-isoborneol and (±)-borneol

respectively, the idea being one or the other of the enantiomeric alcohol would react faster depending on the steric fit in the transition state (kinetic resolution). The camphor formed was partially optically active and isolated from the reaction mixture as its acid-soluble oxime, the rotation of which is opposite to that of the parent camphor³⁹. The results are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—PARTIAL KINETIC RESOLUTION OF ISOBORNEOL AND BORNEOL

Entry	Ketone	Camphor-oxime from IsoB		Camphor-oxime from B	
		α_{D}^{30}	% e.e. ^a	α_{D}^{30}	% e.e.
1	(—)-Menthone	—37.8°	89	+6.48	15.3
2	(+)-3-Methylcyclohexanone	—3.1°	7.3	+0.36	1
3	(+)-Fenchone ^b	—29.55°	70	— ^c	—
4	3-Cholestanone	—3.8	9	+0.42	1

^aBest value of several runs is given; the maximum rotation of camphor-oxime is taken as $[\alpha_{\text{D}}]$ 42.4°. ^bFenchone used was of 16.2% optical purity; the rotation value is corrected for the enantiomeric purity of the ketone. ^cNo pure camphor-oxime could be isolated due to contamination of fenchone-oxime.

XIII

XIV

XV

In case of isoborneol, the (—)-enantiomer was consumed faster giving (+)-camphor which in turn formed (—)-oxime. This is in accord with the reagent attacking the cyclohexanone ring from the equatorial side (β -face) with the larger group, C_1 -methyl, away from the β -substituent at C_3 of the ketones. The case with (+)-fenchone* is different but similar result is expected. High kinetic resolution brought about by menthone compared to 3-methylcyclohexanone is evidently due to the influence of multiple chiral centres in the former.⁴⁰ Incidentally, this procedure provides a useful and convenient method of configurational correlation for a chiral ketone. With (\pm)-borneol also, the (—)-isomer was used up faster giving (—)-camphor⁴¹ and (+)-oxime showing that the C_1 -methyl of borneol still acts as the bulkier side of the molecule overriding the effect of the pendant gemdimethyl group. However, the extent of kinetic resolution is extremely low which is inconsistent with the usually high asymmetric induction brought about by borneol-reagent elsewhere¹. The present low value is possibly due to the fact that the only substituent which can effectively interfere with the C_6 -methyl is at C_3 of the ketone and is too far away to have the dominating effect previously encountered. The opposing influence of an "acyclic" transition state (X) as the steric encumbrance increases may also be partly responsible.

Next, we investigated the effect of addition of Lewis acid, especially anhydrous magnesium bromide, to the ketone prior to reduction. The object was to increase the reducibility of the ketones⁴² and also to shift the "cyclic" transition state towards the "acyclic" one by breaking open the $C=O..Al$ bond. This would result, according to our hypothesis, in an increase of asymmetric induction with isoborneol-reagent, offer a better reducing possibility to borneol-complex, and eliminate the effect of the pendant gemdimethyl group, at least partially, in the latter. To take the last case first, reduction of acetophenone and isobutyl methyl ketone with (—)-bornyloxyaluminium dichloride in presence of anhydrous magnesium bromide (1.5 mol) yielded an alcohol containing slight excess (2–3%) (Table 5) of the S-enantiomer. This indicates that the steric interference of C_6 -methyl is still dominant but considerably damped possibly by a change in the transition state model. Unfortunately, none of these ketones could be reduced by the reagent in absence of anhydrous magnesium bromide and so no clear conclusion can be drawn regarding the quantitative aspect of this effect and its relation to the two transition state models (X and XI). Only two cases are known, namely, the reduction of benzaldehyde-1-d¹ and phenylglyoxylic acid³⁴, where the stereoselectivity is very high (33 and 57% respectively) and at the same time opposite to

TABLE 5—ASYMMETRIC REDUCTION OF KETONES IN PRESENCE OF ANHYDROUS $MgBr_2$

Entry	Ketone	$MgBr_2$	α_D^{20} with IsoB ^a	% e.e.	α_D^{20} with B ^a	% e.e.
1	PhCOMe	nil	+10.92°	25(R) ^b	—	—
2	"	1.5 mol	+0.92°	2.1 (R)	—1.0	2.3 (S)
3	Me ₂ CHCH ₂ COMe	nil	—1.02°	5 (R) ^c	—	—
4	"	1.5 mol	—2.2°	10.5 (R)	+0.6	3 (S) ^d
5	Me ₂ CHCOMe	nil	—0.8°	15 (R) ^d	—	—
6	"	1.5 mol	—1.17°	22 (R)	—	—

^aIsoB and B stand respectively for (—)-isobornyloxyaluminium and (—)-bornyloxyaluminium dichloride.
^bConfig in parenthesis. ^cMaximum rotation reported, α_D^{20} 20.85°. ^dMaximum rotation, α_D^{20} 5.34°.
^eBorneol does not reduce these ketones in absence of anhydrous $MgBr_2$.

* The result of kinetic resolution with fenchone reported by Morrison⁴⁰ is in variance with that of ours.

that expected on the basis of the preferred transition state (X). For the latter, an alternative suggestion has been made³⁴ that the carboxylate anion might be effectively bulkier than phenyl, particularly on account of it being complexed with aluminium salt. There could even be a second possibility that the carboxylate anion be better placed gauche to the positive dipole, OAlCl_2 , thus upsetting the stability order of the four competing transition states, as in the reduction of trifluoromethyl phenyl ketone.

It is interesting to note that both isobutyl methyl and isopropyl methyl ketone were reduced by (—)-isobornyloxyaluminium dichloride in presence of anhydrous magnesium bromide with much higher (almost double) asymmetric induction (Table 5) than in absence of it. Prediction based on the present models thus proved correct.

Phenylmethylcarbinol suffered extensive racemisation with anhydrous magnesium bromide, which accounts for its low stereoselectivity, (ca 2%), almost identical for borneol and isoborneol. It may be pointed out that addition of anhydrous magnesium halides in Grignard reduction inhibited the reduction considerably in favour of the addition reaction,⁴² which was regarded as a good proof for Whitmore cyclic mechanism⁴³. The present experiments, however, show that in absence of the competing addition reaction, the reduction is also facilitated by Lewis acids. A different mechanism has recently been suggested⁴⁴ for the increase of the ratio of addition to reduction in Grignard reaction by added salts.

Experimental

Materials and Instruments : (+)-camphor and (—)-bornyl acetate were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company, Inc. The former was reduced by lithium aluminium hydride to a mixture of (—)-isoborneol (90%) and (+)-borneol (10%)⁴⁵ and used in place of (—)-isoborneol. Phenylglyoxylic acids were prepared following known procedure^{46,47}. All ketones were purified by distillation or crystallisation. Solution of lithium aluminium hydride was made in ether of approximately 1M strength and was standardised before use against iodine solution in benzene according to Felkin's procedure⁴⁸.

The g.l.c. analysis was carried out using a column (6ft. \times $\frac{1}{4}$ in.) consisting of 10% polyester of diethylene glycol adipate (DEGA) and alternatively succinate (DEGS) supported on Gas-chrom-Z (60-80 mesh).

The optical rotation were taken on Hilger Micro-optic Photoelectric Polarimeter, Model 511.2/60207.

Reduction Procedures : All reductions were carried out in duplicate at least. In most of the cases, the variation in asymmetric induction was slight and the best value was taken. Some of the earlier experiments¹⁵ were repeated and the revised data supplied in the Tables. The following methods were employed for reductions.

Method A : To an ice-cold solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.0 g, 0.06 mol) in ether (60 ml) was added 1M ethereal solution of lithium aluminium hydride (15 ml, 0.015 mol). After a few min, (—)-isoborneol (or borneol) (9.3 g, 0.06 mol) in ether (15 ml) was added dropwise until the evolution of gas ceased. A slight excess of the alcohol was generally taken to avoid any unreacting hydride. The reaction vessel was taken out of the ice-bath and the ketone (0.05 mol) in ether (20 ml) was added within 15 min, the mixture stirred at room temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ h, and then cautiously decomposed with ice-cold 4N sulphuric acid. The ethereal layer was separated, washed free from mineral acid, and solvent evaporated through a Vigreux column. The crude product was analysed by gas chromatography for any unreacting ketone. The alcohol was separated as described under 'purification'.

Method B : An ethereal solution of lithium aluminium tetra-alkoxide was prepared either by the action of (—)-isoborneol (or borneol) (9.3 g, 0.06 mol) on lithium aluminium hydride solution (1M, 15 ml, 0.015 mol) or by reaction of (+)-camphor (9.2 g) in ether (50 ml) with the same amount of lithium aluminium hydride solution under gentle reflux for 4 h. To this solution, the ketone (0.05 mol) in ether (20 ml) was added all at once, followed by dropwise addition of a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (8 g, 0.06 mol) in ether (60 ml). The rest of the operation was the same as in Method A.

Method C (with Anhydrous Magnesium Bromide) : A solution of anhydrous magnesium bromide was prepared⁴⁹ by dropping dry bromine (13.2 g, 0.08 mol) onto magnesium turnings (2.0 g) in ether (24 ml). After the reaction was complete, the ketone to be reduced (0.056 mol) was added to it and the mixture stirred for 1 h. To this was now introduced a solution of (—)-isobornyloxy-(or bornyloxy)-aluminium dichloride (0.06 mol) prepared by Method A, during 10 min with efficient stirring. After 1 h, the mixture was cooled and decomposed carefully with 4N

sulphuric acid and the product was worked up as before.

Method D (Inverse Addition) : In one reduction of isobutyl methylketone, the preformed reagent from (—)-isoborneol according to Method A was added dropwise to a solution of the ketone in ether. The asymmetric induction was found to be exactly the same (5%) as in Method A.

Purification of the Alcohols : (a) The alkylmethylcarbinols were distilled out from the crude reaction product through a Vigreux column as already described in an earlier paper¹². The distillate was converted into acid phthalate by heating with phthalic anhydride in pyridine. The latter was taken up in aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate solution, washed free from any neutral matter with ether, and the alkaline solution acidified to afford in each case a gummy product. This was hydrolysed with aqueous 10% potassium hydroxide solution and the alcohol extracted with ether and distilled through an efficient fractionating column. Distillate was collected with a boiling range of 2° and the purity of the alcohol checked in each case by g.l.c. The IR spectra of each sample was also compared with those of pure authentic racemic alcohol. The reduction of alkyl methyl ketones was carried out only by Method A and by Method C (in presence of anhydrous magnesium bromide). The results are shown in Table 5.

(b) Phenylmethylcarbinols were purified from the crude reaction mixture by steam distillation which removed most of the camphoraceous material, followed by extraction of the aqueous solution with ether. Removal of ether and distillation in vacuum afforded almost pure alcohol which was further purified by conversion into acid phthalate and regeneration as reported elsewhere¹². The yield of recovery was 50-60% ; and the reduction was complete in each case except for the methoxyphenyl ketones. The purity was checked by g.l.c. and also by IR. Phenyl-*t*-butylcarbinol was purified by preparative gas chromatography on a column of carbowax and was obtained as a solid, b.p. 110°/7 mm. The product from reduction with (—)-isobornylaluminum dichloride had a rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 9.0^\circ$ in C_6H_6 solution, corresponding to optical purity of 35%. The optical rotation of these substituted phenylalkylcarbinols was determined in neat and in case of phenylmethylcarbinol also in methylene dichloride solution, the maximum rotation reported⁴⁹ being $[\alpha]_D^{23} 52.5^\circ$. The reduction was carried out mostly

by Method A and some by both Method A and Method B with comparable results.

(c) The mandelic esters in the crude reaction mixture was initially freed from camphoraceous matter by prolonged steam-distillation. The residue on distillation in high vacuum afforded pure esters. These were hydrolysed by refluxing alcoholic 10% potassium hydroxide solution for $\frac{1}{2}$ h on the water-bath. Extraction with ether and acidification of the alkaline solution yielded solid mandelic acids. These were filtered, dried in vacuum, and rotation measured in aqueous or alcoholic solution. In a typical experiment, ethyl phenylglyoxylate was reduced with (—)-isobornylaluminum dichloride according to Method A. The mandelic ester, as purified above, was hydrolysed and the corresponding mandelic acid had a rotation, $\alpha_D^{30} + 22.2^\circ$ (EtOH), corresponding to optical purity of 14%. A portion of the same ethyl mandelate (2.7 g) was reduced in ethereal solution by lithium aluminium hydride to phenylethylene-1,2-glycol (1.5 g), m.p. 60-62°. It had an optical rotation, $\alpha_D^{30} + 5.7^\circ$ corresponding to 14% optical purity, (α_D^{max} 40.6°).

*Resolution of (±)-*p*-nitrophenylmethylcarbinol* : To a solution of the acid phthalate of (±)-*p*-nitrophenylmethylcarbinol, m.p. 156° in ethyl acetate (100 ml), (—)-brucine (22.3 g) was gradually added. The mixture was heated on the steam-bath at 80-90° with a little more of ethyl acetate to make a homogeneous solution. It was kept for a few days at room temperature. The yellow crystalline precipitate (10 g) was crystallised several times from ethyl acetate until no change of rotation was observed for the salt. It was then decomposed with concentrated hydrochloric acid in the cold. The acid phthalate thus obtained was crystallised from ether-petroleum and had m.p. 100°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 32.77^\circ$ (EtOH), *c* 1.15, 0.5 dm). The IR spectra were superimposable with those of an authentic racemic sample. On hydrolysis with aqueous 10% alkali, it furnished (—)-*p*-nitrophenylmethylcarbinol, b.p. 160°/6 mm, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 73.6^\circ$.

Procedure for Kinetic Method of Resolution : In a typical experiment, reagent from (±)-isoborneol (or borneol) (3.08 g, 0.02 mol) was prepared according to Method A. To this solution, was added (+)-3-methylcyclohexanone⁵⁰ (1.12 g, 0.01 mol) in ether (10 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. The product was worked up in the usual way. The residue after evaporation of ether was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.4 g) and sodium acetate (2.8 g) and sufficient methanol to

make it homogeneous. The solution was refluxed for 1 h, diluted with water, and extracted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). The petroleum extract was shaken vigorously with 4N sulphuric acid (3×25 ml). The acidic solution was neutralised with saturated sodium carbonate solution. The oxime separated as white crystalline solid which was collected by filtration, washed with water, and dried to a colourless powder (0.68 g), m.p. 102°; $\alpha_D^{25} + 3.1^\circ$ (c, 1.47 in EtOH). In case of other ketones, the mixture was stirred overnight after the addition of ketones. However, four hours were found to be sufficient in all these cases.

Acknowledgment

We are deeply indebted to Dr. H. Felkin of Gif-sur-Yvette, France for helpful comments, to Dr. Amitava Ghosh of Bose Institute, Calcutta for g.l.c. analysis, to Dr. E. L. Eliel of North Carolina University, USA for a gift of (+) fenchone, to Dr. J. Verghese of Christian Medical College, Vellore, India for a gift of (+)-pulegone, to Drs. G. Sarker and C. K. Ghosh for assisting in some of the experiments, and Dr. S. C. Pakrashi of Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta for valuable cooperation.

References

- Part II, D. NASIPURI, C. K. GHOSH and R. J. L. MARTIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 657.
- E. J. COREY, R. J. MCCAULLY, and H. S. SACHDEV, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 2476; E. J. COREY, H. S. SACHDEV, J. Z. GOUGOUTAS, and W. SAENGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 2488; F. WUDL and T. B. K. LEE, *Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 61.
- W. VON E. DOERING and R. W. YOUNG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 631.
- G. VAVON, C. RIVIERE, and B. ANGELO, *Compt. rend.*, 1946, **222**, 959; G. VAVON and B. AGNELO, *Compt. rend.*, 1947, **224**, 1435.
- H. S. MOSHER and E. LACOMBE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3994.
- A. STREITWEISER, J. R. WOLFE and W. D. SCHAEFFER, *Tetrahedron*, 1959, **6**, 338; B. BELLEAU and J. BURBA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5751; G. VAVON and A. ANTONINI, *Compt. rend.*, 1950, **230**, 1870; 1951, **232**, 1120; A. C. MUTTRIC and J. B. CARR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 2648.
- O. CERVINKA and O. BELOVSKY, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1965, **30**, 2487; and earlier papers.
- S. R. LANDOR, B. J. MILLER and A. R. TATCHELL, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1966, 2280; 1967, 197.
- For a review, see J. D. MORRISON and H. S. MOSHER in "Asymmetric Organic Reactions", Prentice-Hall Inc., New Jersey, 1971, p. 160.
- E. L. ELIEL and D. NASIPURI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 3809.
- D. NASIPURI and G. SARKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 165.
- D. NASIPURI and G. SARKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 425.
- E. L. ELIEL and M. N. RERICK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1367.
- M. S. KHARASCH and O. REINMUTH in "Grignard Reactions of Nonmetallic Substances", Prentice-Hall Inc., New Jersey, 1954, p. 147.
- D. NASIPURI, G. SARKER and C. K. GHOSH, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 5189.
- D. NASIPURI, C. K. GHOSH, P. R. MUKHERJEE and S. VENKATARAMAN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1971, 1587.
- E. L. ELIEL, *Record Chem. Prog.*, Kresge-Hooker Science Library, 1961, **22**, 129; E. C. ASHBY and J. PRATHER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 729.
- D. MEA-JACHEAT and A. HOREAU, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Soc.*, France, 1966, 3040.
- J. S. BIRTWISTLE, K. LEE, J. D. MORRISON, W. A. SANDERSON and H. S. MOSHER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 37.
- G. D. HEDDON and W. B. BROWN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3744.
- J. H. BREWSTER in "Elucidation of Organic Structures by Physical and Chemical Methods", (Ed.) K. W. BENTLEY and G. W. KIRBY, Wiley Interscience, New York, vol. 4, part III, p. 1.
- M. CHEREST, H. FELKIN and N. PRUDENT, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 2199.
- V. E. ALTHOUSE, E. KAUFMANN, P. LOEFFLER, K. UEDA, and H. S. Mosher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3138.
- G. J. KARABATSOS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1367.
- H. C. BROWN and K. ICHIKAWA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 373.
- G. CHAUVIERE and Z. WELVART, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, France, 1970, 774.
- J. MATHIEU and J. WEILL-RAYNAL, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, France, 1968, 1211.
- D. CABARET and Z. WELVART, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 1064.

29. D. NASIPURI, Abstracts Part II, Second Indo-Soviet Symposium on Chemistry of Natural Products, New Delhi, 1970, p. 100 ; Abstracts, Chemical Convention, India, 1969, p. 255.
30. L. Pauling in "The Nature of Chemical Bond", 3rd. edn., Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N. Y., 1960, p. 255.
31. C. AMSTERDAMSKY, G. CHAUVIERE and Z. WELVART, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, France, 1968, 4859.
32. D. NASIPURI, K. MITRA and S. VENKATARAMAN, *J. C. S. Perkin Tran. I*, 1972, 1836.
33. J. D. MORRISON in "Survey of Progress in Chemistry", (Ed.) A. F. SCOT, Academic Press, New York, 1966, vol 3, p. 166.
34. D. NASIPURI and C. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 556.
35. E. KNORR, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3175.
36. V. PRELOG, M. WILHELM, and D. B. BRIGHT, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 221.
37. J. D. MORRISON and H. S. MOSHER, Unpublished results cited in ref. 9, p. 202.
38. H. S. JOHNSTON in "Advances in Chemical Physics", (Ed.) I. PRIGOGINI, Interscience Inc., New York, 1961, vol. 3, p. 131.
39. I. HEILBRON and H. M. BUNBURY in "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, vol, 1, p. 415.
40. J. D. MORRISON, A. TOMASH and R. W. RIDGWAY, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, 565.
41. A. FREDGA and J. K. MIETTINEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1947, 1, 371 ; K. FREUDENBERG, *Angew. Chem.*, 1953, 65, 259 ; M. G. NORHOLT and J. H. PALM, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1966, 85, 143.
42. C. G. SWAIN and H. B. BOYLES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 870.
43. E. S. GOULD in "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Reinhart, and Winston, New York, 1964, p. 546.
44. M. CHASTRETTE and R. AMOUROUX, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 470.
45. D. S. NOYCE and D. B. DANNY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5743.
46. T. WIELAND, *Ber.*, 1948, 81, 314.
47. V. N. GUPTA and T. R. SESHADRI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1956, 44a, 223.
48. H. FELKIN, *Bull. Soc. Chim., France*, 1951, 18, 347 ; D. C. AYRES, D. N. KIRK, and R. SAWDAYE, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1970, 505.
49. U. NAGAI, T. SHISHIDO, R. CHIBA and H. MITSUBASHI, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, 21, 1701.
50. E. J. EISENBRAUN and S. M. McELVAIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 3383.